

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Purpose of the study: Due to the industrialization of teachers' social functions, the changing of the principles that characterize the preparedness to make decisions, the development of uniqueness and thinking style of modern teachers, the increasing requirements for the training of future teachers in the Pedagogical University, the need for meaningfulness of professional self-determination and mastery of professional. The essay identifies variables that develop primary school teachers' communication skill. Methodology: Monitoring communicative competence allowed the teacher to compare communication skills and abilities in the control and experimental groups. Results: The article defines the content and structure of the concept "professional competence of the teacher"; communicative competence is presented as a key component of the high professional level of primary education teachers; the analysis of the structure of communicative competence, including such components as communicative knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as three levels of formation of primary school teachers' communicative competence; the involve a lot.*

Keywords: *education, formation, communicative competence, primary school teacher.*

To improve the communicative competence of a primary school teacher, you need to know the characteristics of the children with whom you have to work.

Studying the characteristics of modern younger schoolchildren, it is necessary to turn to the psychological portrait of modern children.

How are these children different from previous generations?

This is the "information technology" generation. Many schoolchildren are connected with each other through the Internet, computers. They have become dependent on these technologies, the views and beliefs of the majority are shaped by the Internet. The nature of thinking is also changing - it becomes "clip", characterized by fragmentation and superficiality. It is easier for students of this time to read some small article, mini news. One of the features of modern children is also distinguished by "life" in the virtual world. Children would rather play some kind of computer game than go outside or visit friends. In connection with the loss of communicative, real, living human ties, analysts point to the danger of the formation of certain syndromes in the modern generation.

First, it is hyperactivity. Many children suffer from Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. And every year, you can see it in your classes, their number is growing. These children are not focused, restless, disinhibited, and as a result hyperactive. They often have learning problems, although they may be gifted in some particular areas of activity. But this does not mean at all that these children are gifted - they often have problems of a medical and psychological nature, violations of the age-related development of the nervous system.

Secondly, a tendency to autism, i.e. these children are immersed in their own world, living in dreams and fantasies, moving away from reality.

Values are also changing: more and more children are striving for personal self-improvement, competition sometimes to the detriment of others, and moral values, such as helping others, empathy among modern schoolchildren, are losing their relevance, the authority of social activities is also falling. In connection with taking into account the psychological characteristics of primary school children, there are “Tips” for modern teachers that will help build the right style of communicative interaction with schoolchildren. When working with such children, it is necessary to structure the educational process well. It is important for students to receive accurate information: what, why and in what time frame they need to do. At the same time, it is important to set visible and realistic goals so that the child learns to work on his own, and not for adults (parents) to do for him because too much is given or too heavy, “incomprehensible” material. The information you present to students should not be "redundant". It is difficult for children to perceive a lot of information, attention begins to dissipate, so it is also important to divide the lesson into several parts, with switching activities. The concept of knowledge and the structure of knowledge in various cases are defined. The concept of a language designed to extract, store and transmit information requires the study of methods and mechanisms for representing knowledge in a language. Knowledge and its representation are the key problems of the cognitive sciences in general and cognitive linguistics in particular. From the point of view of linguoculturology, knowledge is considered as the result of cognition of the surrounding world, as an adequate reflection of reality in the human mind, as a product of the processing of verbal and non-verbal experience, which forms the "image of the world". ”, on the basis of which you can make your own judgments and conclusions [1].

Most cognitivists agree that knowledge in the human mind consists of mental representations built from concepts, analogies, images, relationships between elements within a single mental space. It is recognized that knowledge is not an amorphous entity; it is structured to represent certain blocks of information, which led to the use of the term "knowledge structures". It is noteworthy that this phenomenon is known under various names of “knowledge repositories”, “encyclopedic knowledge”, “knowledge base”, “background knowledge”, “knowledge formats”, etc. Despite some terminological inaccuracy, general knowledge structures are understood as blocks information containing a system of interrelated concepts.

There are different types of knowledge structures: linguistic (vocabulary, grammar, phonetics, word formation, etc.); encyclopedic (worldview, history, politics, economics, nature, etc.), communicative (communicative goals and intentions, conditions and circumstances), cultural (literature, art, cultural values, customs and traditions, etc.). All these types of knowledge are combined into two main groups: linguistic knowledge and non-linguistic or knowledge about the world represented in the human mind. The problem of relations between knowledge structures and their verbal explications is a key issue in cognitive linguistics [2]. In this regard, the key task is to determine which elements of the language are most relevant for knowledge representation. Knowledge structures are represented in the human mind in the form of "frames" (a stereotypical situation and its verbal representation), "scenarios" (a stereotypical dynamic sequence of events, episodes, facts), "gestalts" (a single structure that combines both). emotional and rational components).

The concept of knowledge structures turns out to be very important for cognitive stylistics and, in particular, for text interpretation. The interpretation of the text is considered as a purposeful cognitive activity aimed at understanding and perception of information transmitted by the text.

The interpretation procedure consists in constructing and testing a hypothesis about the deep information of the text. Cognitive linguistics states that interpretation must be carried out within certain modules of understanding:

- use of language knowledge;
- construction and testing of hypothetical interpretations;
- building a "model world" of the text;
- reconstruction of the author's ideas;
- establishment of relations between the "inner world" of the addressee and addressee [3].

One of the most significant tasks involved in interpretation, from a linguistic point of view, is to locate the primary language signals and markers that should direct the interpretation process. When seen in this light, linguistic units are intended to reflect various kinds of knowledge systems that are of special significance. This is because the structures of knowledge and the conceptualization of those structures contribute to the building of the "model world" of the text as well as the reconstruction of the author's own reality.

Our findings have shown that the use of stylistic devices is an essential component in the process of representing different types of knowledge systems. In this context, the use of stylistic elements in a literary work such as allusion, symbol, and anthomasia—technologies that fulfill the pragmatic role of "activating knowledge structures"—can serve as an indicator. When we talk about activation, we are referring to the process by which specific regions of the brain get excited throughout the course of speech activity as a result of the effect of verbal signals that are intended to reflect certain knowledge structures [3]. On the basis of this, an inference can be drawn that some language units in a piece of literary writing are utilized with the deliberate goal of activating knowledge structures that are pertinent to the conceptual information presented in the text. Under the impact of specific verbal signals, a certain contour scheme (frame) is activated; nevertheless, many slots of this frame remain unexplained and implicit. This is how the process of activation of knowledge structures in the text may be represented. Examining frame relationships, having encyclopedic knowledge, and making contextual connections to the linguistic stimulus signal are the three things that need to be done in order to explain these slots.

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